

THIAZOLIDONES. PART V. SYNTHESIS OF 5-ALKYL/BENZYL-2-ARYLIMINO-4-THIAZOLIDONES

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α -Bromo-fatty acids and α -bromo- β -phenylpropionic acid have been condensed with arylthioureas to yield the title compounds.

α -Bromo-fatty acids (from propionic, butyric^a and caproic^a acids) have been condensed with arylthioureas in presence of sodium acetate to yield 5-methyl/ethyl/butyl^a-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidones. In order to obtain thiazolidones with a benzyl group on C₅, α -bromo- β -phenylpropionic acid has been condensed with arylthioureas, yielding 5-benzyl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidones.

EXPERIMENTAL

Substituted phenylthioureas were prepared from the corresponding amines. α -Bromo-fatty acids were prepared by bromination of propionic, butyric^a and caproic^a acids (Vogel, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 1951, p. 421). α -Bromo- β -phenylpropionic acid was prepared as described in "Org. Syn." (1941, 21, 99).

Condensation of substituted phenylthioureas with α -bromo-fatty acids and α -bromo- β -phenylpropionic acid was carried out as described by Raval and Trivedi (this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 733). Thiazolidones (yields about 60%) were crystallised from ethanol (Table I).

TABLE I

5-Alkyl/benzyl-2-arylimino-4-thiazolidones.

No.	R.	X.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	Me	<i>o</i> -Cl	128°	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₂ ClS	12.8	13.0
2.	"	<i>p</i> -Br	165°	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₂ BrS	11.0	11.2
3.	"	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	294°	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ ON ₂ S	14.3	14.5
4.	"	2,4-DiCl	184°	C ₁₀ H ₆ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	11.6	11.6
5.	"	2,5-DiCl	294°	"	11.4	"
6.	"	3,4-DiCl	174°	"	11.8	"
7.	"	<i>p</i> -n-OC ₄ H ₉	225°	C ₁₅ H ₂₃ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.4	10.5
* 8.	Et	H	154°	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ ON ₂ S	14.6	14.5
9.	"	<i>o</i> -Cl	125°	C ₁₁ H ₉ ON ₂ ClS	12.4	12.6
10.	"	<i>m</i> -Cl	144°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ON ₂ ClS	12.8	12.6
11.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	154°	"	12.5	"
12.	"	<i>p</i> -Br	148°	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ ON ₂ BrS	10.5	10.7
13.	"	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	104°	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	13.8	13.7

* Dixon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, 71, 635, records m.p. 148-49°.

TABLE I—*contd.*

No.	R.	X.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
14.	..	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	140°	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	13.5	13.7
15.	..	2:4-DiCl	130°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	10.8	11.0
16.	..	2:5-DiCl	154°	..	11.0	..
17.	..	3:4-DiCl	132°	..	11.2	..
18.	..	<i>p-n</i> -OC ₄ H ₉	100°	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.2	10.0
19.	<i>n</i> -Bu	H	144°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ ON ₂ S	13.1	12.9
20.	..	<i>m</i> -Cl	115°	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ ON ₂ ClS	11.2	11.3
21.	..	<i>p</i> -Cl	136°	..	11.4	..
22.	..	<i>p</i> -Br	136°	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON ₂ BrS	10.0	9.8
23.	..	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	98°	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ ON ₂ S	12.1	12.2
24.	..	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	136°	..	12.4	..
25.	..	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	118°	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	11.7	11.5
26.	..	2:4-DiCl	104°	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	10.0	10.1
27.	..	3:4-DiCl	144°	..	9.9	..
28.	-CH ₂ Ph	H	183°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ON ₂ S	11.4	11.3
29.	..	<i>o</i> -Cl	149°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ ON ₂ ClS	10.0	10.1
30.	..	<i>m</i> -Cl	163°	..	10.2	..
31.	..	<i>p</i> -Cl	212°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ ClS	10.3	10.1
32.	..	<i>p</i> -Br	217°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ON ₂ BrS	9.0	8.9
33.	..	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	128°	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ ON ₂ S	10.9	10.8
34.	..	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	138°	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.4	10.3
35.	..	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	187°	..	10.1	..
36.	..	2:4-DiCl	138°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	9.0	9.1
37.	..	2:5-DiCl	206°	..	9.2	..
38.	..	3:4-DiCl	218°	..	9.3	..
39.	..	<i>o</i> -COOEt	167°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₂ S	9.2	9.0
40.	..	<i>p-n</i> -OC ₃ H ₇	161°	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.6	9.4
41.	..	<i>p-n</i> -OC ₄ H ₉	141°	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.2	8.4

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